

THE IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPING PRESENTATION SKILLS OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract

In the globalized era, these days the formation of applicable skills among students is associated not only with becoming proficient at a high level of communicative proficiency, but also with a complex of technologies that allow understanding the modern methods of teaching languages. Since most students struggle with having a public speech in front of audience, the ability to succeed in speaking has been considered as an integral part of professional quality of future teachers. We take the view that students need good communication skills for different academic and social contexts, so that this study deals with bringing out the main importance of boosting PPT skills.

Keywords: Technology, PowerPoint, Classroom, Innovative, Traditional classroom.

Today, PowerPoint, as a significant part of Language Learning, is a much widely-used presentation software for it consents a language teacher to present his or her lesson with colored texts, images with simple animation, sound and etc. Presentations are becoming an integral part of language teaching, especially in learning language. Teaching students to design effective presentations assumes two objectives, namely, enabling students to function successfully in the future professional surrounding, and preparing them for their possible further academic career.

Moreover, as stated Joe Dale, there is a great importance of combining novel technologies not as a bolt on or reward, but as an integral part of the teaching and learning process. The ability to speak well enough to interest, influence or persuade other people is a major asset, whatever you choose to do in the future. Additionally it allows the learners to encourage the four “C’s” such as Communication, Creativity, Collaboration and Critical Thinking [3]. Being able to speak in front of an audience is considered as one of the greatest sake for every individual that is taken from higher education. During my academic year by preparing power point presentations, I was able to boost my speaking ability in front of the audience.

Students need a thorough in-depth instruction and practice in order to present an effective spoken communication. One of the best practice is to give oral

presentations. As Morley stated an oral presentation skills are essential for employability and true academic study as they lead students to enter into debate and sustained reasoning [4]. Presentation skills are essential, since they aid them to develop competencies in an area of their future working places and demonstrate their ability to communicate. In addition, this software allows the integration of visuals and sounds. Abraham Oommen said that PowerPoint presentation appeals learners' diverse learning styles, such as visual, auditory, kinesthetic, and creative by employing multimedia methods such as sounds, colour, images, action, design and so on [2].

On the one hand, Lanius, C states that another important benefit of PowerPoint presentations for the instructors is that instructors can have face-to-face communication with learners contrary to the conventional chalkboard teaching where instructors often face the chalkboard with their back to the class [5]. On the other hand, Akdağ and Tok's study discovered that the instruction done with the support of power point presentation has a detrimental role on students' success, approximately 88.5% of the students reported that the usage of power point helps them better acquire and better understanding of the course material, we can infer that using PPT in FLE courses has a positive effect on their learning [1]. To be more specific, the plethora of students considered that preparing power point presentation is likely to influence for their future career path, not only for the purposes of conveying meaning but also making productive lessons.

To conclude, by utilizing the communicative method of teaching for learners in order to prepare and deliver presentations on certain topics, we prompt them to collaborate, to speak, to share ideas, to organize their thoughts and present them in a convincing and self-confident way to achieve their task and in order to meet the audience's expectations. By this way, the students will have the chance to improve their communicative competence and presentation skills. Language and communicative competences are being developed based on a lot of preparation and practice. Universities should offer the students a great chance to improve their ability to communicate professionally in a work, academic or in a social environment in order to become competent speakers.

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